

Impact of Recruitment and Selection on Workplace Dynamics

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Abstract

The objective of the study is to see how Recruitment and Selection affects Workplace Dynamics. The data is collected via a structured Questionnaire, and seeks to correlate how, for different demographics of the respondents, the answer to the same question would vary. This study could help set a base for any changes in organizational structure. As found out in this study, there is no direct relation between the given demographic of the respondent, and the profession that they are in, no matter for how long. However, there seems to be a close relation with the respondent's method of Recruitment & Selection into an organization, in any role, with the effect of that method playing a part into their work ethic.

Keywords: recruitment, selection, workplace, employee, organization, respondent, internship.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research background and Context

In the modern workplace, there are three types of employees. The first are those that positively impact the workplace, the second are those that impact it negatively, and the third are those that have no effect on the workplace in any way, shape, or form. However, there is reason to believe that the way they interact with the workplace, as an employee, is based on how they interacted with the company in the first place.

The prospective candidate, at the time of recruitment, would have a particular sense and image about the company. This is what would have caused them to apply to said company. Recruitment is the process of discovering and catching qualified or appropriate applicant to fill the vacant position (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021). Now, when the prospective candidate sits for the interview process, in whatever way is the company policy, they observe their surroundings, and start changing their original opinion and image of the company. During the interview itself, they would be considering what the interviewers say, how the interviewers react to their (the candidate's) questions, as well as what is offered to them, in whichever job role they have applied for. After the interview is concluded, the candidate will be re-assessing whether to accept the job role if it is offered to them. If it is not offered to them, they are free to apply for another job elsewhere. However, if the job is offered to them, and they accept it, they will now work for the company. They may have a different view of the company, now that they can see the inner workings of it. Given what their new view is, and their personal characteristics, they will affect the dynamics of the team they are working in. Not at the beginning, but the longer they work in the same team, they will have an influence in the dynamics of the team, right from the overall presentation of projects to the tardiness of the group as a whole.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study aims to check how Recruitment and Selection affects the employee, who had a certain image of the company before applying and getting selected, can affect the dynamics of a workplace. This is a qualitative study, and as a result, there will not be a lot of depth with respect to the final results, or a final decision to be made on the basis of numbers. This was just done to ensure a fair perspective across all possible demographics. The study will also aim to show how opinions may differ with the age of the person who participated in this study.

1.3 Significance of the study

The significance of the study is such that it can help understand how the different demographic of prospective candidates and employees share common or different opinions, and how they could be related to their specific demographic. It would also highlight any particular wantings, with respect to how a particular demographic views their organisation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction to Literature Review

The current chapter aims to review and analyse different literature works on the topic of research and try to identify the research gap to cater to that gap through this research. Given that the study conducted is qualitative, it will be slightly different to some of the works that have been reviewed.

2.2 Factors affecting Recruitment and Selection

One of the foremost factors that affect Recruitment and Selection of a prospective candidate, as an employee is the age of the candidate. It is to be noted that anyone under the age of 18 years is generally considered a “child” globally. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No. 138), “This fundamental convention sets the general minimum age of admission to employment or work at 15 years (13 for light work) and the minimum age for hazardous work at 18 (16 under certain strict conditions). It provides for the possibility of initially setting the general minimum age at 14 (12 for light work) where the economy and educational facilities are insufficiently developed.” This helps curb child labour and exploitation of children across the globe, especially in work that may not be fit for their particular demographics of age and gender.

While performance is usually a legitimate selection criterion, hiring decisions are complex and do not rely on any single factor. Impression Management may influence decisions makers’ perceptions on a broad range of important factors such as ambition, interpersonal skills, or general fit (Zhao and Liden, 2011).

A company's recruitment policy is created in the atmosphere in which it works. Policy, as defined by Cole and Kelly Uzodika and Subban (2018), is a declaration of behaviour philosophy intended to influence behaviour and choices. The recruiting policy specifies the employment goal and provides a structure for implementing the recruitment process (Boscal, 2015).

Employers' choices on staffing are important to the operation of enterprises and have a wide range of effects that affect individuals, organizations, and society. In this sector, the most fundamental issue is why companies hire people in the first place. Managers in charge of recruiting employees must be equipped with the skills and capabilities required on every job and determine if candidates exhibit these traits. Interviews, reference checks, tests, applications, and curriculum vitae can all help discover inconsistencies in applicants. If management has a greater knowledge of the applicants' benefits and limits, they may create excellent recruiting decisions (Torlak, Kuzey & Ragom, 2018).

The main goal of the selection method is to find and recruit the best candidate(s) for the open positions (Louw, 2013). Recruiting a large number of individuals is simple, but choosing the best among them may be difficult for businesses (Boscal, 2015).

Furthermore, to choose the finest candidates, academics have backed a multilayer fitting selection method, such as "Person-Job Fit" and "Person-Organization Fit" (Chuang et al., 2016; Anderson et al., 2004; Kristof-Brown et al., 2002). There are a variety of additional ways for selecting the proper candidates (Schmidt & Hunter, 1998); although, applicants' selection procedures vary for each organization (Branine, 2008).

2.3 Tactics used during Recruitment & Selection

During the course of recruitment and selection, there could be various methods and tactics used by interviewers. According to Newell and Tansley (2001), interviews seem to be the most frequent method of staff selection. Organizational management advantages from the use of interviews since they get to meet the applicants in person. During the interview, individuals will have the chance to learn more about the commercial and public sectors. The selection interview's objective is to gather as much information as feasible and then use that information to make a decision (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018). A structured interview, according to Stoner et al., (2015), is one in which the interviewer asks questions from a prepared list and does not stray from it except for a few follow-up questions. The structured interview asks each candidate the same fundamental questions, allowing for easier comparability between candidates. An interviewer can prepare employment-related questions ahead of time and then perform a standardised interviewee assessment form using this sort of interview (Phillip A., Ishaq, and Kola, 2023).

Recruitment can be seen as a positive, while selection can be seen as a negative. The reason being, recruitment locates all applicants and gives them an equal chance to be selected, but selection involves screening candidates to identify the most qualified for the positions made available. Selection shortlists the candidates to a smaller number. During the selection process, candidates will be subjected to different tests, situations, to help the recruiters understand their individual capabilities. This may also help them eliminate candidates who they feel may not make the cut in their organisation.

Furthermore, to choose the finest candidates, academics have backed a multilayer fitting selection method, such as "Person-Job Fit" and "Person-Organization Fit" (Chuang et al., 2016; Anderson et al., 2004; Kristof-Brown et al., 2002). Individuals are usually asked to complete an examination to define whether or not they are experienced to accomplish the work if recruited. The most common form of employment assessment that prospects are exposed to is a medical examination. Only those applicants who require the physical capability to do their duties are submitted to a medical examination, often known as pre-placement medical examinations (Mathis & Jackson, 2006).

A personality test is a test that is administered to a candidate in the hopes of predicting the sort of personality the applicant possesses and how that personality will impact work performance (Harries, 2000). Personality, on the other hand, is context-dependent, as it evolves through time. Extroversion, emotional stability, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness are among the five qualities measured in the personality test. The most reliable predictor of work performance is the conscientiousness measure. Individuals who are tenacious and have a feeling of responsibility do better at work. However, this is not a very accurate indicator of work success, according to Olatunji and Ugoji (2013).

If their applications are approved, prospects are typically requested to give the names and contact information of people who can serve as references. Reference checks are usually performed over the phone and are used to verify the information given by the candidate. Although most references are apprehensive to respond to particular questions (Mathis & Jackson, 2006), a background check can be utilized to gather as much information as feasible that will be used in deciding whether or not to approve the applicants. References, therefore, provide company information into how other people see the candidate's main skills. The company should contact the individual's previous workplace and acquaintances.

2.4 Challenges faced during Recruitment & Selection

There are a few challenges that are faced by candidates and the recruiters alike, during recruitment and selection. To start with the recruiters, they may have been given specific criteria, when looking for potential candidates for a particular position. Salary ranges, age restrictions, experience in a similar field, certain certifications, or licenses etc. They have to then find suitable candidates, locate their profiles across whatever platforms they use, get the resume and/or CV of the potential candidate, following which they have to establish contact with the person, usually via an email or a phone call. In the case of an email, the recruiter has to play a waiting game with the person, with no idea if the email was even seen. In the case of a phone call, there will be a higher chance of being answered, regardless of the outcome. Here, the recruiter can either schedule an interview or strike out that name, saving them precious time to go further into their search for another candidate.

Now, from the candidates' point of view, they may not want to apply for the job for a few reasons, the main reason being the salary offered. This could be 90% of all cases where recruiters are turned down. Apart from the salary offered, rejection could be on the basis of job location, and the candidate may not want to relocate at all, no matter what. Another reason that the candidate may not want to join would be that they may have to travel a lot, and they are not comfortable with that. These are just a few of many reasons the candidate may not want to join the organisation.

Even if the candidate is agreeable to join the organisation, it is not a guarantee that they will stay for long. They could clear all obstacles placed in front of them, get the offer letter from the organisation, and then not sign it at the end. They could have had a change of heart, or gotten a better offer from somewhere else. Whatever the reason, the recruiter is now in a tough spot, given that they may have sacrificed other candidates for this particular individual. The recruiter would have to now convince the candidate that their organisation is better, or they would have to match the offer that has caused the candidate to rethink their position.

While recruitment and selection remain an integral part of a company, it must also evolve with time. Standard questions and standard situations, along with cliché topics of discussion, remain the focal point of many an interview. While this does give a clearer picture than other unconventional methods, things become repetitious after a while, and the value of the interview goes down. This in turn will affect the candidates' view of the company, which in turn will affect their performance when employed, which in turn will affect the company's output in that particular domain. The present research aims to find out how the candidate was affected by their interview, and how it may or may not have changed after working in the company. It is a qualitative study, not a quantitative study.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Nature/Type of Research

This research is a primary data-based one. It is not descriptive, nor is it quantitative. It is purely qualitative in nature.

3.2 Data Collection

The data collected for this research is all primary data. It was collected via a structured questionnaire, which was not a physical form, but an online Google Form. The form was circulated online, across various social media, to gain as much traction as possible. The data was collected from different people, from various backgrounds. No personal information like name, email ID, phone number was collected, so as to maintain anonymity of the respondents. The only shortcoming in this method is that we cannot collect in-depth information. Whatever data is used, is viable only for short-term. Hence, this kind of data is valuable for HR Managers, to help them fix the problems of the 'here and the now' in the 'here and the now'.

3.3 Sample & Sampling Procedure

In this study, the goal was to get as many people to respond as possible, so the form was left open from 18th June 2024 till 30th June 2024. During this time, the form was filled by 76 individuals, all of whom are above the age of 18 years. The collected data will be used to explore how the individuals' have been affected by their recruitment and selection into an organisation, and how they may or may not be affected their respective team dynamic. All 76 responses will be considered while analysing the data. Here, we have considered the individuals to be either working professionals, or interns in any organisation, in any capacity.

3.4 Period of Study

We can do a cross-sectional study to understand how the respondents feel about their work life, and how their perspective of their organisation has changed, from before they were working there to where they are now. This method aims to provide a picture of the overall situation.

3.5 Research Methodology

In this study, we will be studying the responses of each question, and see how one relates to the next, and if there is any particular trend being followed, based on the answers, or if there is any similarity between answers, based on the demographic of the respondent. Once a particular trend is identified, it can be elaborated upon.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

4.1 Overview of Chapter

This chapter aims to look at all the results of the questions, analyse them to try and find a trend/trends, and further elaborate upon them. Graphical representation is provided for effective interpretation and lastly, a conclusion is provided. Moreover, the data analysed below is collected from 76 research participants through a questionnaire provided using a survey link.

4.2 Analysis of Data

The form was divided into 4 sections. The 1st section was just the title and description of the form itself, as shown below.

FIGURE 1: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 1

The 2nd section involved obtaining the demographics of the respondents, through various questions, as shown below.

FIGURE 2: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 2

There are only 4 questions in this section, as shown on the next page.

FIGURE 3: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 2

From here is where the responses start.

Analysis of the first question

What is your age?

76 responses

This graph represents the age of respondents, majority of whom are between the ages of 18 and 25 years. This means that they are either students or working professionals with about 3-4 years of work experience, at the maximum, assuming they finished their Undergraduate Degree and went right into the workforce. The next greatest group is from the age of

26 to 30 years. Very few people are above 30 years of age. The lack of participants in 30 and above years of age also implies a lack of opinion from a slightly more experienced individual. Determining age groups is crucial for identifying whether age is the impacting factor for certain beliefs or opinions of individuals.

Analysis of the second question

What is your Gender?

76 responses

This question asks for the Gender of the respondent, and this is a very crucial demographic, given that the gender of the respondent could be a strong factor in any inherent biasedness towards the answering of other questions in this survey. Out of the 76 respondents, 43 were male. This may lead to a slight impact on the way the responses are recorded.

Analysis of the third question

What is your current profession, at the time of answering this Questionnaire?

76 responses

Here, we get a clear understanding of the current profession of the respondent. As suggested by the first question of this section, with reference to the respondent's age, a vast majority of them are students. Exactly 38 of them are pursuing a Post Graduate Degree, with another 19.7% are pursuing an Under Graduate Degree. This further implies that the respondents have done a minimum of one internship, at some point in their academic life. The minority of respondents were Business Persons, and just over a quarter were Service Persons. This question was asked to try and back up the first question, as much as possible, to understand how that segment of responses was divided. Of course, there would also be service people and business people in the age of 18-25, but they would again be a minority in that zone.

Analysis of the fourth question

Have you been in an Internship before?

76 responses

This question was used as a determining factor for the next section of the form, which would be the respondent’s last section before submitting. A simple question about having done an internship before or not. Now, coincidentally, the percentage of people who have said yes, is the sum total of all the students, according to the third question (50%+19.7%=69.7%). We can hence go with the assumption that the students are the only ones who have replied yes to this question. We could be wrong as well, but that is not for speculation. So, we can also raise a speculation that the remaining 30.3% of people who had replied no to this question, jumped right into a job role. This is where the form splits. If the respondent said yes to this question, they are taken to section 3, and if they said no to this question, they are taken to section 4. Further questions are asked with respect to each section.

This section aimed to try and find out about the respondent’s internship experience, from the beginning, till the end.

FIGURE 4: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 3

There are 6 questions in this section, as shown below.

FIGURE 5: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 3

The responses for the questions begin on the next page.

Analysis of the first question

How long were you in your Internship for?

53 responses

This graph shows the duration of the respondents' internship. A majority of them have done an internship between 1 and 3 months. Evidently, this suggests that the company has a good environment overall, for someone to work in, especially if they are not working individuals yet. We are still working with our assumption from 2 pages ago, that the people answering this question are all students. We are not taking into consideration about whether the internship is unpaid or paid. The next highest count is for the standard 1 month internship, which is common in the Under Graduate Degree Programs. Surprisingly, a lot of people have done an internship of more than 6 months, which would lead us to suggest that they really enjoyed working in the company.

Analysis of the second question

What was the process in which you were brought into the Internship?

53 responses

According to this, almost half of the respondents went into their internships through a personal contact. This means that they did not really have to worry about getting in the company, speaking candidly. A minority got their internship via cold emailing, so they may not have been expecting to get into the company. They would have been emailing other companies at the same time. The remainder of the respondents got third party help, which could have been online sites, help from their college or something else. These people would have been sure about the company in which they wished to enter, or at least the sector and/or industry that the company worked in.

Analysis of the third question

Were you interviewed before you started your Internship?

53 responses

An almost integral part of entering a company in any level, the interview is something everyone has to go through. Maybe not for an internship, but for a job role, it is a must. Here we can see that almost 80% of the respondents have had to give an interview before starting their respective internships. This accounts for 42 respondents. The others who did not give the interview number only 11. This could be due to the fact that they went into their family business, or the company did not feel the need to conduct any form of interview, or perhaps they went to a friend's family business, where they were well known.

Analysis of the fourth question

If you said "Yes" to the previous question, how did the interview affect what you thought of the Organisation?

44 responses

This is the only optional question in this section of the questionnaire, and while it should have had only 42 responses, a couple of people might have felt that they should answer it even though they had not answered "Yes" to the previous question. Here, we see an interesting dynamic. A whole 25% of the respondents said that the interview did not affect their view of the organisation, but 9.1% said that the interview negatively impacted their view of the organisation. The remainder of the respondents say that they saw the organisation in a more positive way, than they did before their interview. This is an important factor when we take into consideration the next question, which deals with the aftermath of giving the interview and starting work in the organisation. So, we can say that there is a positive correlation between being interviewed and the interview having an effect on a person's view of the organisation.

Analysis of the fifth question

Did your view of the organisation affect the way you worked during your Internship?

53 responses

Here, we come back to all respondents' answers. The majority of them have expressed that their work was affected by their view of the organisation. This implies that they worked as hard for the organisation, as they valued it and as how they felt valued in it. The minority felt that their work was not affected by their view of the organisation, thereby remaining neutral. They were part of the company for a while, but they did not allow emotions to get in the way. The remainder are not sure if their view affected their work or not. So, their self-awareness is not great, or it could be that they do not care about the quality of their work, as long as they complete it as per the specifications told to them. So we can say that there is definitely a positive correlation between the view of the organisation and the affect it has on the work done during the internship.

Analysis of the sixth question

During your Internship, was there any hostility towards you, from the employees working there?

53 responses

This question was asked to understand how many interns felt that the permanent employees felt about them. With a majority saying that there was no hostility towards them, it indicates that the company was a great place to work at, and there may not have been internal politics making any reference to them. However, more than a quarter of the respondents say that there was hostility towards them. This implies that the respondent would possibly bear ill-will towards the organisation. Once this question was answered, the form was ended and submitted.

The fourth section of the form was related to job experience. The only way to get there was by clicking on the "No" option for the last question of the second section. (Have you been in an internship before?) For those people who clicked on "No", this would be the third section of the form.

This section aimed to try and find out about the respondent’s job experience, from the beginning, till date.

FIGURE 6: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 4

There are 5 questions in this section, as shown below.

FIGURE 7: SCREENSHOT OF SECTION 4

The responses for the questions begin on the next page.

Analysis of the first question

How long were you in the job for?

23 responses

We are continuing with the assumption that the people who filled this form are not students at all. Almost three-quarters of the respondents to this question have been in their respective job for under a year, which could lead us to believe that they are fresh out of their last education, whether Under Graduate, Post Graduate, or Doctorate Degrees. The next highest were those who had between 1 and 2 years of experience, followed by those with more than 10 years of work experience. The greatest minority were those with between 2 and 5 years of experience. There was no respondent who had between 5 and ten years of experience. So, we should expect that this could be a major factor when the respondent answered the remaining questions of this section.

Analysis of the second question

Were you interviewed before you started your Job?

23 responses

Here, almost all respondents say they have given an interview before starting their respective jobs. The few that did not, we can assume that they went into their family business, or they got a Pre-Placement Offer from the company, having interned there before, and that the company really enjoyed having them, that they employed them. We cannot draw any significant relationship between the above two questions at this moment.

Analysis of the third question

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, how did the interview affect what you thought of the Organisation?

22 responses

This is the only optional question in this section of the questionnaire, and while it should have had only 17 responses, a few people might have felt that they should answer it even though they had not answered “Yes” to the previous question. Over here, we see something interesting. A majority of the people claim that their view of the organisation was not affected at all, while a small minority claimed that their view of the organisation was impacted undesirably. The rest of the respondents claimed that they saw the organisation in a more positive light than they did before the interview. This result could be explained by an underlying fact that the respondent was sure which organisation they wished to be a part of, before giving their respective interviews.

Analysis of the fourth question

Once you started working in the Organisation, was there a change in the dynamics of the people around you?

23 responses

This question asks the respondents about a change in dynamics of the people around them, in the workspace. Surprisingly, a majority of the candidates are oblivious to any such change. This means that they are unaware of anything that does not concern them. The next largest group said that there was a change in dynamics of the people around them. This shows that they were well aware of changes, and given that it is with respect to the person, we can assume that the interview has affected their view of the organisation, which has then led to them working with a renewed motivation, which has caused the change in dynamics around them. The last group said that there was no such change in the team dynamics. This could mean that the team was already set in such a way that entrance of another member did not affect them, or that the respondent was adaptable enough to fit into the team without causing a shift in the dynamic. Therefore, the interview may or may not have affected their view of the organisation to the extent that they would be able to, or willing to, change the dynamics of the team with their presence.

Analysis of the fifth question

As you progressed in this Job, did you do anything to improve the Dynamics of the Workplace?

23 responses

The final question of this section aims to find out how the employee felt after working in the organisation. A majority of them said that they worked to improve the workplace dynamics in some way, thereby showing initiative. Of course, the end result cannot be determined, as change is a variable that cannot be quantified, and also occurs all the time. Once this question was answered, the form was ended and submitted.

4.3 Further Analysis

Below are two graphs that represent the first section, that deals with the respondents' demographics.

Graph 1: Age and Gender [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

Graph 2: All Demographics [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

This is a relationship map of the 3rd Section (Internship) as a whole. The Section itself does not take into account the age, gender, or current profession of the respondent. Now, if we start to break down this map on the basis of the above three factors, we can get a greater specific view of each group of respondents. This can be represented in the table below the map.

Map 1: Internship [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

INTERNSHIP

Whatisyourage	WhatisyourGender	WereyouinterviewedbeforeyoustartedyourInternship Count	IfyousaidYestothepreviousquestionhowdidtheinterviewaffectwhatyou Count	Didyourviewoftheorganisationaffectthewayyou workedduringyourInternship Count
18-25	Female	21	19	21
	Male	23	19	23
26-30	Female	3	2	3
	Male	4	2	4
31-40	Female	1	1	1
	Male	1	1	1
41 and above	Male	0	0	0

Table 1: Internship [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

The problem with the table and map is that we can't open it to show each individual case, due to SPSS not being able to accurately display the data in a size large enough. I will do my best to explain the table, though it is too generalised.

Each defined age group had both gender's replying, save the last one. Now, all answered the first question in a Yes or No format: "Were you interviewed before you started your internship?" An almost complete majority of each gender in each age group answered "Yes", and went on to answer the next question, which asked how the Interview affected how they thought of the organisation. The last column asked whether their view of the organisation affected the way they worked. I was unable to get a breakdown of the same, due to limitations within SPSS to provide me that data. However, I do not believe that it would be concrete, whether or not I got the breakdown, since there would be too many unique cases to justify. And given my overall sample size, it would not prove consequential.

This is a relationship map of the 4th Section (Job) as a whole. The Section itself does not take into account the age or gender of the respondent. Now, if we start to break down this map on the basis of the above two factors, we can get a greater specific view of each group of respondents. This can be represented in the table below the map.

Map 2: Job [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

JOB

Whatisyourage	WhatisyourGender	WereyouinterviewedbeforeyoustartedyourJob Count	IfyouansweredYestothe previousquestionhowdid theinterviewaffectwhat youthoughtoftheOrganisation? Count	Onceyoustartedworking intheOrganisationwasthere achangeinthedynamics ofthepeoplearoundyou? Count
18-25	Female	7	6	7
	Male	11	11	11
26-30	Female	0	0	0
	Male	3	3	3
31-40	Female	1	1	1
	Male	0	0	0
41 and above	Male	1	1	1

Table 2: Job [Table Source: SPSS Statistics]

The problem with the table and map is that we cannot open it to show each individual case, due to SPSS not being able to accurately display the data in a size large enough. I will do my best to explain the table, though it is too generalised.

Each defined age group had at least on gender of respondent replying. Now, all answered the first question in a Yes or No format: “Were you interviewed before you started your job?” An almost complete majority of each gender in each age group answered “Yes”, and went on to answer the next question, which asked how the Interview affected how they thought of the organisation. The last column asked there was a change in dynamics of the people around the respondent, once they started working in the organisation. I was unable to get a breakdown of the same, due to limitations within SPSS to provide me that data. However, I do not believe that it would be concrete, whether or not I got the breakdown, since there would be too many unique cases to justify. And given my overall sample size, it would not prove consequential.

5. CONCLUSION

5.1 Key Findings

Looking at the facts, we can say that while gender and age are not absolute factors, but rather the interview taken and everything related to their Recruitment & Selection into the company, in the capacity of either intern or full-time employee (in any post).

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations of this study are as follows:

- This study is a purely qualitative study, and so the results should not be considered as a pure study that can be implemented across all types of sectors, industries, and companies.
- However, we can use the Key Finding as given above as a basis for conducting further study, and each company can use a derivation of this study to be conducted every six months or just before a major hiring timeline, to understand how they should be either changing or improving their methods of Recruitment & Selection.
- The companies' study could be more in-depth than the one used here.

5.3 Limitations of the Study

While this study was conducted, there were some limitations that I must acknowledge.

- Firstly, this survey was kept open from 18th June 2024 till 30th June 2024. So, in such short time, there was not a lot of data collection that could take place.
- Secondly, during these 13 days, there were only 76 responses, and very few people above the age of 30 years responded. This does not help matters, especially if this is to be used as a method of improvement for companies in the future, with reference to Recruitment & Selection. The data is skewed due to the age demographics.
- Thirdly, this study is purely qualitative, so there is no meaningful way to use this data to directly relate it in depth, or specifically to any particular organisation.
- The data provided by respondents is very basic, without any scaling methods involved, and does not offer them a room for explanation. This actually helps us make sure that we have a general idea, not a specific one, about our respondents, with each one's answer being almost unique to all others'.

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ANNEXURE

ANNEXURE 1: QUESTIONNAIRE

Section 2

I) What is your age?

- a. 18-25
- b. 26-30
- c. 31-40
- d. 41 and above

II) What is your Gender?

- a. Male
- b. Female

III) What is your current profession, at the time of answering this Questionnaire?

- a. Student (Pursuing Under Graduation)
- b. Student (Pursuing Post Graduation)
- c. Service Person
- d. Business Person

IV) Have you been in an Internship before?

- a. Yes
- b. No

Section 3

I) How long were you in your Internship for?

- a. Under 1 month
- b. Between 1 and 3 months
- c. Between 3 and 6 months
- d. More than 6 months

II) What was the process in which you were brought into the Internship?

- a. Cold Emailing
- b. Third Party Help
- c. Personal Contact

III) Were you interviewed before you started your internship?

- a. Yes
- b. No

IV) If you said “Yes” to the previous question, how did the interview affect what you thought of the Organisation?

- a. Affected my view of the Organisation in a positive way
- b. Affected my view of the Organisation in a negative way
- c. Did not affect my view of the Organisation

V) Did your view of the Organisation affect the way you worked during your Internship?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Maybe

VI) During your internship, was there any hostility towards you, from the employees working there?

- a. Yes
- b. No

Section 4

I) How long were you in the job for?

- a. Less than 1 Year
- b. Less than 2 Years
- c. Less than 5 Years
- d. Less than 10 Years
- e. More than 10 Years

II) Were you interviewed before you started your Job?

- a. Yes
- b. No

III) If you said “Yes” to the previous question, how did the interview affect what you thought of the Organisation?

- a. Affected my view of the Organisation in a positive way
- b. Affected my view of the Organisation in a negative way
- c. Did not affect my view of the Organisation

IV) Once you started working in the Organisation, was there a change in the dynamics of the people around you?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. I am unaware of such a change

V) As you progressed in this Job, did you do anything to improve the Dynamics of the Workplace?

- a. Yes
- b. No

X-X-X-X-X-X-X-X-X